

Work-related musculoskeletal pain among work-from-home employees of a medical billing company

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Abstract

The emergence of the global pandemic novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has greatly changed the ways on how people live their lives from the usual and has significantly challenged every nation to deal with the economic struggle. Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) are musculoskeletal system abnormalities that are predominantly brought on by the execution of work tasks and the immediate work environment (Govaerts et al., 2021). The aim of this study was to determine the prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal pain in various anatomical areas and its association with individual, work area and ergonomic, and work spending hours among work-from-home medical billers. The questionnaire that was designed by the author is a web-based, self-reporting survey that was sent to all respondents by email and uses the convenience sampling method. The study has a response rate of 54.48% which was participated by thirty-four (34) respondents out of the sixty-four (64) work from home (WFH) employees in a medical billing company. The respondents are composed of 10 males (29.4%) and 24 females (70.6%) between the ages of 18 and 45 years, having both genders with a mean age of 31 who had been working from home for the last three months to one year before they joined the study. The results found that 72.6% of the participants experienced work-related musculoskeletal pain (WRMSP). It also showed that the highest percentage of pain experienced was the low back area, followed by the neck and shoulder and lastly by the upper back suggesting that these are the most prevalent sites. The data identified that 47% of the respondents that use a standard chair without armrest (40%) and no foot rest (68%) are prevalent with low back and neck pain areas. The results suggested that 82% of the participants experienced low back pain as the primary work related musculoskeletal pain in the last 12 months and this results to poor workplace ergonomics, long working hours in front of the computers and minimal to non-physical activities and sedentary lifestyles.

Keywords: *Work-related musculoskeletal pain; Work-from-home employees; Medical billing company.*

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Introduction

The emergence of the global pandemic novel coronavirus (COVID-19) has greatly changed the ways on how people live their lives from the usual and has significantly challenged every nation to deal with the economic struggle. Numerous actions have been taken by the government to retard and prevent the spread of the coronavirus through various means such as total lockdowns, prohibition of non-essential travels and recreational activities (Chen, 2021), which also led to retrenchment of employees and closure of various companies that were severely affected by this pandemic.

One of the major changes that has impacted the world's economy and has widespread across every country is the teleworking or working from home (WFH) (Kitagawa et al., 2021) to prevent the spread of the disease in work office engagements. The advantages of distance work are known to increase productivity, less stress, better work-life balance, reduced commuting time and increased control of work pattern and being in less contact with others (Ipsen et al., 2021). Conversely, forced home confinement during lockdowns to control the spread has led to several disadvantages of working from home which includes higher stress levels, disturbed sleeps and insomnia (Pinto et al., 2020) and work-related musculoskeletal pains.

Work-related musculoskeletal disorders (WMSDs) are musculoskeletal system abnormalities that are predominantly brought on by the execution of work tasks and the immediate work environment (Govaerts et al., 2021). Numerous epidemiological studies indicate that workers who use computers frequently get musculoskeletal problems (Kalinienė et al., 2016). Repetitive activity, excessive force, poor posture, contact pressures, vibration, and physical exhaustion are the most significant physical risk factors for WMSDs in many professions (Rahimi Moghadam et al., 2020). The development of musculoskeletal disorders has also been associated to components of workstation design, including the frequency and duration of breaks from the computer, the use of the keyboard, the condition of the computer monitor, the type and use of computer-connected devices, and psychosocial factors (Taieb-Maimon et al., 2012).

The aim of this study is to determine the prevalence of work-related musculoskeletal pain in various anatomical areas and its association with individual, work area and ergonomic, and work spending hours among work-from-home medical billers.

Participants and Methods

The study has a response rate of 54.48% which was participated by thirty-four (34) respondents out of the sixty-four (64) work from home (WFH) employees in a medical billing company through the convenience sampling method. The respondents are composed of both genders consisting of 10 males (29.4%) and 24 females (70.6%) between the ages of 18 and 45 years, having both genders have a mean age of 31 who had been working from home for the last three months to one year before they joined the study.

The questionnaire that was designed by the author is a web-based, self-reporting survey that was sent to all respondents by email. It is intended to evaluate the physical activities, working conditions and the common work-related musculoskeletal pain (WRMSP) experienced by the respondents who are medical billers and are working from their home.

The questionnaire is comprised of three sections. The first part of the questionnaire informs the participant's personal characteristics such as age, gender, height, weight, body mass index (BMI) and level of physical activities. The second phase of the questionnaire establishes the work home setup and the ergonomic properties of their work area such as computers being used, type of desk and chairs, use of foot stool while working and duration of work.

Finally, the third part of the questionnaire aims to identify the prevalence of WRMSP complaints using a standardized Nordic musculoskeletal questionnaire methodology that allow comparison of low back, neck, and shoulder complaints for use in epidemiological studies with good reliability and validity results (Crawford, 2007). The questionnaire consists of nine body

areas that commonly result in WRMSP complaints, but for this study, it would only focus on the respondents' neck, upper back, lower back, shoulders, wrist, and hand areas.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Personal characteristics of participants (n=34)

Characteristics	N	(%)
<i>Gender</i>		
Male	10	29.4%
Female	24	70.6%
<i>Age</i>		
18-25	6	17.6%
25-35	19	55.9%
35-45	9	26.5%
<i>BMI</i>		
Underweight	1	2.9%
Normal Weight	14	41.2%
Overweight	6	17.6%
Obese	3	8.8%
Not determined	10	29.4%
<i>Light Physical Activity</i>		
Almost none	13	38.2%
< 2 hrs/wk	8	23.5%
2-4 hrs/wk	7	20.6%
> 4 hrs/wk	6	17.6%
<i>Heavy Physical Activity</i>		
Almost none	19	55.9%
< 2 hrs/wk	5	14.7%
2-4 hrs/wk	6	17.6%
> 4 hrs/wk	4	11.8%

The data of the personal characteristics of the participants is shown in Table 1. As mentioned earlier, there were more females (70.60%) who participated in this study than males (29.4%). Among the 34 participants, the largest age group belongs to ages 25 to 35 years of age (55.9%) followed by the age group of 35 to 45 (26.5%). Majority of the participants have a normal body mass index (BMI) (41.2%) and 38.2% almost do not perform any light physical activities, while 55.9% were not even performing any heavy physical activities.

Table 2. Work area and ergonomic characteristics of the participants (n=34)

Characteristics	N	(%)
<i>Type of Computers</i>		
Desktop	20	58.8%
Laptop	14	41.2%
<i>Workspace</i>		
Private Room	14	41.2%
Shared Room	7	20.6%
Living Room	12	35.3%
Dining Area	1	2.9%
<i>Type of Chair</i>		
Regular home chair	15	44.1%
With arm rest	2	5.9%
No arm rest	13	38.2%
Adjustable office chair	4	11.8%
<i>Type of Desk</i>		
Computer table	22	64.7%
Dining table	6	17.6%
Folding table	3	8.8%
Makeshift table	3	8.8%
<i>Use of Footstool</i>		
Yes	7	20.6%
No	27	79.4%

The data on work areas and ergonomic characteristics of the participants are shown in Table 2. There were 58.8% who prefer to use desktop computers while working from home and majority of them are working in their private rooms (41.2%). Computer table shows the highest percentage choice of desk type resulting in 64.7% and since the respondents are working from home, the majority opted to use a regular home chair (44.1%), followed by without any arm rest (38.2%). Many of the respondents are not using footstools (79.4%) while working at home.

Table 3. Work spending of the participants (n=34)

Characteristics	N	(%)
<i>Time spent working from home</i>		
4-6 hours	2	5.9%
6-8 hours	10	29.4%
8-10 hours	15	44.1%
> 10 hours	7	20.6%
<i>Workspace</i>		
< 5 hours	3	8.8%
5-10 hours	23	67.6%
> 10 hours	9	26.5%

The work spending characteristics of the respondents are tabulated in Table 3. Most of the participants are spending eight (8) hours to ten (10) hours of work (46%) of their time and usually spend five (5) to ten (10) hours (70%) of their time using their keyboards while working.

Table 4. Distribution of WRMSP of the participants (n=34)

WRMSP IN THE LAST SEVEN (7) DAYS										
Gender	Neck		Shoulders		Wrist / Hand		Upper Back		Low Back	
	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)
Male	4	12%	3	9%	3	9%	3	9%	6	18%
Female	6	18%	9	26%	11	32%	13	38%	13	38%
Total	10	30%	12	35%	14	41%	16	47%	19	56%
WRMSP IN THE LAST TWELVE (12) MONTHS										
Gender	Neck		Shoulders		Wrist / Hand		Upper Back		Low Back	
	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)
Male	7	21%	6	18%	6	18%	5	15%	9	26%
Female	18	53%	19	56%	16	47%	18	53%	19	56%
Total	25	74%	25	74%	22	65%	23	68%	28	82%

Low back pain is the most reported pain experience (56%) followed by upper back pain (47%) in the last seven days by the time that the questionnaire was given to them. However, low back pain is the highest reported by males (18%) followed by neck pain (12%), while the females' highest reported pain was equally shared by upper back and low back pain (38%) followed by the wrist and hand pain (32%) in the last seven days. Conversely, in the last 12 months, as shown in Table 4, in general, low back pain (82%) is still the most reported WRMSP followed by neck pain and shoulder pain both at 74%. Nonetheless, females reported that shoulder and low back share as the highest reported pain at 56% followed by neck and upper back at 53%, while males reported low back pain (26%) as the top most experienced WRMSP followed by neck pain (21%) in the last 12 months respectively.

The prevalence of low back was seen in most respondents who are not performing light (38%) and heavy (53%) physical activities. Exposure to ergonomic stresses at work, as well as environmental, psychological, and/or individual risk factors, are connected to work-related LBP (Wami et al., 2019). It is also associated with participants that spend eight (8) hours to ten (10) hours (41%) of work from home; and use keyboards for five (5) to ten (10) hours (53%) while working from home. Low back pain is commonly seen in respondents who are using a regular or standard chair (56%) having no arm rest (32%) to support their upper arm. Interestingly, 68% of participants reported not using footstool while working are complaining of low back pain.

Neck and shoulder share the second most common complaints of WRMSP. Desktop users (41%) that use regular home chairs (50%) report pain in these areas. At the same time, working for eight (8) to ten (10) hours (41%) contributes to the symptoms while sitting in a regular chair (50%) without using a footstool (65%) as well.

Upper back is the third most commonly seen WRMSP condition seen in this study. These are experienced by 24% of overweight respondents that usually do not involve in any light (26%) nor heavy (41%) physical activities. The upper back pain is seen in those who spent eight (8) to ten (10) hours of work (35%) using a regular chair without any arm rest (26%).

Discussion

The current study examined the work-related musculoskeletal pain of the medical billers that are working from their home during the COVID-19 pandemic. Overall, it is found that 72.6% of the participants experienced WRMSP. The result showed that the highest percentage of pain experienced was the low back area, followed by the neck and shoulder and lastly by the upper back suggesting that these are the most prevalent sites. According to Jung et al. (2021), sitting posture can affect the trunk muscle activity and slumped sitting significantly decreases the activities of the internal obliques and transverse abdominis. Working for prolonged hours, like in this study, for eight to ten hours, contributes to slouched position considering that 56% using non-ergonomic chairs that could support the back and neck areas. In the activities of working in front of the computer, the upper trapezius muscle is the most tensed muscle, leading to the production of internal force in the body, which in turn will cause muscle tension and pain in the shoulder and neck (Condrowati et al., 2020) and this suggests that the neck and shoulder are the second most common WRMSP in this study.

The data identified that respondents who use a standard chair without armrest (38.2%) and no foot rest (79.4%) are prevalent with low back and neck pain areas. Roelofsen (2002) suggests that ergonomics is significant because performing a particular repetitive task induces the body to tense up and exhibit symptoms like weariness, discomfort, aches, and tension. This results in musculoskeletal disorders that hinder performance.

Conclusion

The results suggested that 82% of the participants experienced low back pain as the primary work-related musculoskeletal pain in the last 12 months and this results to poor workplace ergonomics, long working hours in front of the computers and minimal to non-physical activities and sedentary lifestyles.

The study has several limitations. The sample size of the study might be insufficient due to the limited number of participants and limited time in collecting the data. Finally, the possibility of a bias of the respondents as they may not probably remember the entire problem during the last 12 months when answering the self-reported questionnaire. Future research is suggested with a larger sample size and longer of period of time to further identify the WRMSP in work-from-home medical billers.

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